

WITH THE HELP OF EDUCATIONAL TOOLS IN COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOLS TEACHING CHEMISTRY

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Abstract: Currently, in the introduction of modern educational standards, attention is paid to the educational methodology based on combined methods of the educational program. This article provides information about the advantages of using computer technologies in the methodology of teaching chemistry. Through this methodology, the teacher will be able to use it to expand the students' chemical knowledge and to better explain the essence of chemistry to the students. The opinions and comments of experienced pedagogues about the modern methodology of teaching chemistry are presented. In the teaching of chemistry in schools, it is appropriate to use computer educational technologies to further strengthen students' knowledge of the essence of chemistry and the subjects of chemistry.

Keywords: Education, pedagogical skills, modern educational tools, teaching technologies, chemistry education, educational efficiency.

Introduction

To date, we can consider that the attention to the development of methods based on educational tools in the field of education and in the development of a new modern methodology of education is at a high level. The use of methodological programs of modern education in the development of educational tools serves to improve the quality of education. In the development of methods based on such educational tools, teachers should have a high level of pedagogical skills and psychological potential to increase students' interest in science and attract their attention.

In this scientific study, training was conducted based on information on increasing the effectiveness of education with the help of modern educational programs and teaching technologies. Based on this information, questionnaires were organized among teachers and students. Many people have approved the ideas that teaching modern methods through computer technologies is effective and high-quality in the educational system. The results of our research showed that the use of computer tools in the organization of teaching technologies in modern educational programs is a way to improve the quality of education. The idea of computer-aided teaching appeared in the mid-50s. During this period,

several approaches to teaching using computer technologies were formed. The first concepts were introduced by English cybernetics G. Pask and American psychologists N. Crowder and B. Skinner. The ideas expressed by them are still relevant today, and are in many ways suitable for assessing the main reasons for the low effectiveness of traditional education. They believed that the educational process should have a quick (flexible) adaptation to the individual characteristics of students. Thus, B. Skinner argues that one of the main reasons for the ineffectiveness of the modern education system is that a whole group of students tries to learn at the same speed. It is obvious that this delays students who can move faster. It is not clear how this approach harms students who learn the material slowly. A slow learner need not be dumbed down, but in a traditional system, he or she quickly falls behind and has no ability to progress at the teacher's chosen pace. Using properly designed computer programs, the slow learner can progress to a level of development that we have not yet dreamed of, if he can work at his own pace. Computer technology and software have undergone qualitative changes in recent years and can be used effectively in training. At this stage, the use of computer technology for teaching has gone beyond the level of technology. Teaching technology means a set of pedagogical techniques, teaching methods and pedagogical measurement technologies of the teacher, which ensures the repeated and effective achievement of the set educational goal and the monitoring of effectiveness at all stages of education.

Computer teaching technologies are a set of pedagogical measurement technologies based on the teacher's pedagogical technique, teaching methodology and the use of computer tools, which ensure the repeated and effective achievement of the specified educational goal and efficiency at all stages of education. provides tracking. Accepting these definitions, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "computer-based teaching technologies" and "computer-based technologies in teaching". The first describes the entire educational process, and the second refers to its individual elements, for example, the use of computers in the individual work of students, the use of computer knowledge management tools. In order to evaluate the didactic possibilities of modern computer technologies in education, we consider the educational process using computer technologies in general and its features in relation to chemistry education. Evaluation of the effectiveness of computer-assisted teaching methods is usually given in comparison with traditional methods and is limited to the measurement of learning outcomes, sometimes taking into account the cost of students' time. Applying this approach

to the assessment of information technology in education means that the latter does not add anything new to the goals and objectives of education. In fact, the introduction of information technologies changes the quality of education itself, changes it in accordance with the general principles of informatization of society, in the way of turning it into an information society. This is one of the most important aspects of introducing new educational information technologies (YaTAT) into education. The parallel transmission of audio and visual information distinguishes multimedia from hypertext, which allows for navigation in large arrays of textual information (for example, references and help in computer programs). It should be noted that multimedia cannot be reduced to a simple video recording that excludes elements of interactivity and active activity. The use of multimedia in American schools began in 1986. since then, a lot of experience has been accumulated that reveals a number of advantages of using multimedia for educational purposes. Computer teaching technologies are a set of pedagogical measurement technologies based on the teacher's pedagogical technique, teaching methodology and the use of computer tools, which ensure the repeated and effective achievement of the specified educational goal and efficiency at all stages of education. provides tracking. Accepting these definitions, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "computer-based teaching technologies" and "computer-based technologies in teaching". The first describes the entire educational process, and the second refers to its individual elements, for example, the use of computers in the individual work of students, the use of computer knowledge management tools. In order to evaluate the didactic possibilities of modern computer technologies in education, we consider the educational process using computer technologies in general and its features in relation to chemistry education.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we support the opinion that the use of modern educational tools through chemistry teaching techniques in schools increases the quality of education. With the help of computer technologies, we can bring modern methods and new information about science based on the technologies of teaching chemistry. In order to further increase the interest of students in the teaching of chemistry, we can provide them with new information about the science and video-audio textbooks about the science. It is possible to increase the effectiveness of education by forming the technique of teaching chemistry through modern educational programs.

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